

Supplementary Information: Effect of Quantum Delocalization on Temperature Dependent Double Proton Transfer in Molecular Crystals of Terephthalic Acid

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1 OK structure of the three forms of Terephthalic Acid.

As mentioned in the main paper, Terephthalic acid exists in three polymorphs, namely, form I, II and III. While the lowest energy one, i.e., form I has been described in the main paper, here we discuss the results of form II and III. Figure S2 and S3 show the structure of form II and III respectively. The main difference between form I and the other forms is the stacking of the two layers. While in form II, the -COOH groups of two molecules in a chain that are involved in H-bonding, are stacked above the benzene ring of TPA in the layer below it, in form I and III, the molecules are perfectly stacked on top of each other. Additionally, in form I and II there are improper weak interchain H-bonds. Compared to form I, in form III, two neighbouring chains are shifted with respect to one another thereby disrupting the interchain C-H \cdots O H-bonds. This also results in doubling of the cell size in form III. Table S1 compares our computed values of lattice parameters with the experimental results. We found that they are in reasonably good agreement. Further, from the computation of the cohesive energy, we find that while they are similar in form I and II, the TPA molecules are weakly bound in form III.

Table S1: Comparison of the lattice parameters and cohesive energies (ΔE^{coh}) of the three polymorphs of TPA.

Form	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	α (°)	β (°)	γ (°)	Vol. (Å ³)	ΔE^{coh} (eV/mol.)
I	9.625	7.606	3.623	73.80	105.07	139.44	165.13	1.811
I-exp ¹	9.54	7.73	3.75	70.85	107.36	137.78	174.76	
II	9.623	5.247	4.945	85.76	136.10	104.36	165.17	1.809
II-exp ¹	9.54	5.34	5.02	86.95	134.65	104.90	172.77	
III	8.899	10.449	3.612	86.30	89.36	91.06	335.12	1.748
III-exp ²	8.940	10.442	3.79	90.0	91.21	90.0	353.72	

Figure S1: Crystal structure representation of TPA (form I) using ball and stick representation. (a) Side view (along the chain axis) represents the stacking of molecular chains (b) Top view (along z axis) shows layer-layer overlap. Top layer atoms in solid balls and bottom layer atoms as points. Green, red and white balls represent carbon, oxygen and hydrogen respectively

Figure S2: Crystal structure representation of TPA (form II) using ball and stick representation. (a) Side view (along the chain axis) represents the stacking of molecular chains (b) Top view (along z axis) shows layer-layer overlap. Top layer atoms in solid balls and bottom layer atoms as points. Green, red and white balls represent carbon, oxygen and hydrogen respectively.

Figure S3: Crystal structure representation of TPA (form III) using ball and stick representation. (a) Side view (along the chain axis) represents the stacking of two molecular chains (b) Top view (along z axis) shows layer-layer overlap. Top layer atoms in solid balls and bottom layer atoms as points. Green, red and white balls represent carbon, oxygen and hydrogen respectively.

2 Convergence of PIGLET simulation w.r.t the number of beads.

PIGLET simulations uses path integral formulation of statistical mechanics to incorporate NQE. In this approach, the quantum nucleus is transformed into a classical ring polymer of “ P ” beads/imaginary time slices where each bead is connected to (two) neighbouring beads through harmonic potential. In the limit $P \rightarrow \infty$, the transformation is exact and gives accurate quantum statistics of the nuclear system. However, in reality only a finite number of beads are used. Hence, it is necessary to perform convergence tests of the relevant properties with respect to the number of beads. Since the number of beads is inversely proportional to the temperature, convergence tests need to be performed at the lowest simulation temperature. In our study 70 K is the lowest temperature. Therefore, we have performed convergence test of the following thermodynamic quantities with respect to the number of beads at 70

K: (i) Potential Energy (Figure S4(a)) and (ii) quantum kinetic energy (Figure S4(b)). The convergence tests were conducted on 4, 12, 16, 24, 32 and 64 beads where 4 and 12 beads were sampled for for 5 ps and the others for 10 ps. The potential and quantum kinetic energy (per atom) converged at 16 beads.

Figure S4: Potential energy (top panel) and quantum kinetic energy (bottom panel) as a function of the number of beads.

The convergence obtained for the thermodynamic quantities does not guarantee the accurate description of system properties. Hence, additional convergence tests were undertaken for quantities related to the investigation of proton transfers along the hydrogen bond. These are (i) the heavy atom distance (d_{O-O} , Figure S5(a)), (ii) the hydrogen bond angle ($\angle O-H-O$, Figure S5(b)), (iii) the radius of gyration of the proton (r_G , Figure S5(c)) and (iv) the effective free energy as a function of proton transfer coordinates (δ_1 and δ_2 , Figure S6).

The converged number of beads for d_{O-O} and $\angle O-H-O$ is at 12 whereas the r_G needs 16

beads to achieve convergence. The effective free energy as a function of the proton transfer coordinates needs a higher value of 64 beads. The reason for the distribution to not converge has to do with the fact that the proportion of the transferring hydrogen atom decreases as the number of beads increases. This is observed because P is directly proportional to the force constant of the inter bead harmonic potential. Consequently, an increase in the number of beads slows the sampling of the potential energy landscape and would require longer simulation time. Therefore, an overall comparison for all the beads would not be completely relevant to check the convergence as we focus mainly on the nature of the proton transfer. In order to compare the nature of a specific proton transfer, i.e., whether the proton hops or tunnels, the radius of gyration as a function of sampling time is compared with the time evolution of the centroid proton transfer coordinate. The graphs at the two values of “ P ” (16 and 64) are shown in Figure S7. It is observed that nature of transfer does not change when the number of beads is increased from 16 to 64. Hence, 16 beads were used for the PIGLET simulations at all temperatures.

3 NQE and finite temperature effects on double proton transfers.

In the main paper we have discussed the results only for 70 and 300 K. Here we show how the different quantities associated with the DPT evolves with increase in temperature. Figure S8 shows the temperature dependent evolution of the free energy surface as a function of d_{O-O} and the proton transfer coordinate $\delta_{1,2}$, as obtained from the BOMD and PIGLET simulations. $\delta_{1,2}$ has been described in the main paper. While, in the BOMD simulations proton transfers were not obtained until the system attains room temperature, in the PIGLET simulations even at 70 K there are proton transfer events. We observe that as the temperature is increased the free energy difference between the two minima decreases.

In order to investigate whether the double proton transfers are stepwise or concerted, we

Figure S5: Convergence with respect to the number of beads for (a) the heavy atom separation (d_{O-O}), (b) the hydrogen bond angle, ($\angle O-H-O$) and (c) the radius of gyration of the O-H hydrogen (r_G).

Figure S6: The effective free energy as a function of the proton transfer coordinates δ_1 and δ_2 for (a-f) 4, 12, 16, 24, 32 and 64 beads.

Figure S7: The time evolution of the centroid proton transfer coordinate (δ_1^c) and the radius of gyration (r_G) for (a) 16 and (b) 64 beads.

Figure S8: Temperature evolution of the effective free energy as a function of the proton transfer coordinate ($\delta_{1,2}$) and the heavy atom distance (d_{O-O}) obtained from (a) BOMD and (b) PIGLET simulations.

have plotted the free energy surface as a function of the proton transfer coordinates δ_1 and δ_2 . Figure S9 shows the results obtained from BOMD and PIGLET simulations.

Figure S9: Temperature evolution of the effective free energy as a function of the proton transfer coordinates δ_1 and δ_2 obtained from (a) BOMD and (b) PIGLET simulations.

Figure S10 displays the joint density plots of δ_o^c (centroid proton transfer coordinate) and r_G^{\parallel} (component of r_G parallel to the O-H bond) of the transferring protons as a function of

temperature. The increase in temperature from 70 to 300 K leads to the gradual decrease in the spread of the joint distribution around $\delta_o^c = 0.00$. This behaviour reflects the gradual shift in the nature of the proton transfer from tunneling to activated hopping.

Figure S10: Temperature evolution of joint distribution of δ_o^c and r_G^{\parallel} obtained from PIGLET simulations.

4 Weak improper $C - H \cdots O$ hydrogen bonds and its connection to the asymmetry of the DPT.

In addition to the intrachain strong H-bonds, the TPA crystal also has two weak interchain $C - H \cdots O$ H-bonds (wHB1 and wHB2) as shown in Figure S11(a). The respective oxygen heavy atoms for the two wHBs have different bond order which dynamically depends on the position of the proton along the stronger $O - H \cdots O$ bond. Therefore, we plot the joint

distribution between the wHB distance (d_{H1-O_D} in green and d_{H2-O_A} in red) and the proton transfer coordinate ($\delta_{1,2}$) in Figure S11. Irrespective of the temperature and the NQEs effect, we observe that for $\delta_{1,2} < 0$, the two wHB distances (d_{H1-O_D} and d_{H2-O_A}) are different where the shorter (longer) wHB is created from the sp^3 (sp^2) hybridized carboxyl oxygen. On the other hand for $\delta_{1,2} > 0$, the bond order of the two different O heavy atoms (O_D and O_A) interchanges but the corresponding wHB distances do not interchange and attain similar values due to the packing of the crystal. This creates a difference in the crystal environment when the proton is situated at $\delta_{1,2} < 0$ and when it is present at $\delta_{1,2} > 0$. Therefore, the proton experiences an asymmetric potential along the $O-H\cdots O$ bonds and the DPT produces non-degenerate tautomers of 19 meV/DPT junction. It is to be noted that in the case of gas phase TPA dimer the tautomers are degenerate at 0 K as the crystal fields ($C-H\cdots O$ interactions) are non-existent.

Figure S11: The joint density distribution between the wHB ($d_{H1\cdots O_D}$ in green and $d_{H2\cdots O_A}$ in red) with the proton transfer coordinate ($\delta_{1,2}$) obtained from the BOMD (a and b) and PIGLET (c and d) simulations at 70 and 300 K.

References

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